

OXALENEDIAMIDOXIME. PART II.

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In continuation of a previous communication, some further work on the nickel complex elucidating its structure is reported. The preparation and properties of different types of complexes of nickel, cobalt, copper and mercury have also been described.

Although a large volume of literature has accumulated on the complex compounds of dimethylglyoxime since the first isolation of the nickel complex by Tschugaeff in 1905, the analogous dioxime ($\text{NH}_2\text{C}=\text{NOH}$)₂, appears to have been much less systematically studied in its capacity for complex formation with metals and the nature of the complexes formed. The molecule of oxalenediamidoxime is, however, interestingly constituted from these points of view, in that all the three types of chelation which the molecule may give rise to, form 5 or 6-ring systems and are therefore equally probable, viz. (1) simple co-ordination through two NH_2 groups; (2) replacement of H of NOH and co-ordination through one NH_2 ; (3) inner complexes of Tschugaeff's type in which the amino groups play no part.

Dubsky and Okac (*Coll. Czech. Trav. Chim.*, 1932, 4, 588), in their studies on the influence of the vicinity of amino group on the formation of complexes of this dioxime, have described the preparation of the previously known nickel complex (Tschugaeff and Surenjanz, *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 182) and some complexes of copper. Some cobaltous complexes have been described by Schnackig (Dissert., Leipzig Univ., 1938). In furtherance of the work done by these workers, the present author has undertaken a systematic investigation of the complexes of this dioxime with different metals. The anhydrous inner complex of nickel has been described and its usefulness in the direct gravimetric estimation of nickel in presence of other metals has been pointed out in a previous communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 608). Some further work on the constitution of the nickel inner complex and the preparation of different types of complexes of some more common metals are reported in the present paper.

In analogy with dimethylglyoxime (DH_2), oxalenediamidoxime ($\text{NH}_2\text{C}=\text{NOH}$)₂ is simply written as OxH_2 , indicating the two replaceable hydrogen atoms of the two oxime groups. The following is a brief list of the complexes of Ni, Co, Cu and Hg with oxalenediamidoxime.

	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{OxH}_2, 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$
$\text{Ni}(\text{OxH})_2, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{T})$	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{OxH}_2$
$\text{Ni}(\text{OxH})_2$	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 3\text{OxH}_2(\text{S})$
$\text{Ni}(\text{OxH})_2 \cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{I}$	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 3\text{OxH}_2 \cdot 2\text{HCl}$
$\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{OxH}_2$	$\left[\text{Co} \begin{array}{l} (\text{OxH})_2 \\ (\text{NH}_3)_2 \end{array} \right] \text{Cl}$
$\text{Cu}(\text{OxH})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{D})$	$\left[\text{Co} \begin{array}{l} (\text{OxH})_2 \\ \text{Py}_2 \end{array} \right] \text{Cl}$
$\text{Cu}(\text{OxH})_2$	
$\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot \text{OxH}_2$	$\left[\text{Co} \begin{array}{l} (\text{OxH})_2 \\ (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N})_2 \end{array} \right] \text{Cl}$
$\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{OxH}_2$	
$\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{OxH}_2$	$\text{Cl} \cdot \text{Hg} \cdot \text{OxH}$

Compounds marked (T), (D) and (S) were prepared by Tschugaeff and Surenjanz (*loc. cit.*), Dubsky and Okac (*loc. cit.*) and Schnackig (*loc. cit.*) respectively. It may be observed that inner complex formation is common in many complexes. The nickel inner complex belongs undoubtedly to Tschugaeff's type, as probably also the brown amorphous copper complex $\text{Cu}(\text{OxH})_2$. Simple co-ordination compounds are also quite numerous due to ready co-ordination through the amino groups. Chelation of the second type quite probably occurs in the substituted cobaltic complexes, since these are similar to the cobaltamine complexes in general physical properties. The yellow mercuri-complex $\text{Cl} \cdot \text{Hg} \cdot \text{OxH}$ may belong to none of these three types but may simply be a partial salt of the dioxime, only one NOH group entering into combination.

Substitutions at the NH_2 groups are being made in the oxalenediamidoxime molecule, and their effect on complex formation studied.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Nickel bis-oxalenediamidoxime was prepared in the form of light orange, silky needles from a solution of nickel chloride (1 mol.) and oxalenediamidoxime (2 mol.) and rendering the blue coloured solution slightly ammoniacal. The precipitate was well washed with cold water and dried in air. It is insoluble in water and ammonia but soluble in dilute acids. It contains two molecules of water of crystallisation which are readily

lost by drying at 110-20° for half an hour. [Found : N, 38.59; Ni, 20.02. Ni (OxH)₂ requires N, 38.3; Ni, 20.04 per cent].

The magnetic susceptibility of the anhydrous substance was examined in a magnetic balance of the Gouy type (mean H_4 amp = 5158 gauss). The substance was diamagnetic ($\chi_v = -0.393 \times 10^{-6}$) indicating a dsp^2 bonding and hence a planar structure of the molecule.

Attempts to methylate the nickel complex with methyl iodide and dimethyl sulphate gave rise to a methoiodide with the first reagent but no product with the second under conditions in which Barker (*Chem. News*, 1925, 130, 99) isolated methoiodide and methyl sulphate derivatives of nickel dimethylglyoxime.

Assuming Barker's arguments to be correct, the present methoiodide must therefore be represented as

or, what appears to the present author more probable, as

In either formula the difficulty of formation of a doubly linked sulphato derivative is easily apparent. The above experiments in methylation therefore indicate that the nickel dioxime complex is a planar molecule in which the auxiliary linkings through nitrogen (Pfeiffer. *Ber.*, 1930, 63, 1811) appears to occupy *trans* positions.

Nickel bis-oxalenediamidoxime methyl iodide was prepared by heating under reflux a mixture of nickel bis-oxalenediamidoxime (1 mol.) and methyl iodide (2 mol.) in alcohol for several days, till the orange suspension went into solution in alcohol giving a green coloration. On slow evaporation at room temperature, pink coloured crystals were deposited. It was washed

several times with CS_2 and then with ether and dried in air. The compound decomposed slowly on keeping, giving inexact analytical results. [Found : N, 20.8; I, 45.5; Ni, 11.7. $\text{Ni}(\text{OxH})_2 \cdot (\text{CH}_3\text{I})_2$ requires N, 19.4; I, 44.0; Ni, 10.2 per cent].

The probable constitution of this compound has already been indicated. An alternative possibility of methylation at the amino groups is ruled out, since such direct methylation has not been found possible with oxalenediamidoxime (Tiemann, *Ber.*, 1889, 22, 2943, 2955).

Nickel bis-oxalenediamidoxime chloride was prepared by adding a solution of oxalenediamidoxime (2 mol.) to an aqueous solution of nickel chloride (1 mol.) when the green colour of the solution changed to dark blue. The solution was kept faintly acid by adding one or two drops of dilute hydrochloric acid and was allowed to crystallise slowly at the ordinary temperature, when transparent blue crystals, highly soluble in water, were deposited. [Found : Cl, 15.1; Ni, 12.2. $\text{Ni}(\text{OxH}_2)_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cl, 14.99; Ni, 12.4 per cent]. The orange coloured nickel dioxime is precipitated on treatment of the blue solution with ammonia, the change being reversible :

The blue compound is paramagnetic having a magnetic susceptibility approximately equal to a pure nickel salt ($\chi_g = +7.2 \times 10^{-6}$; $\mu = +2.4$ Bohr's magneton). The bonding is therefore sp^3 or simple tetrahedral. The blue colour of the compound is also suggestive of tetrahedral co-ordination.

Cupric bis-oxalenediamidoxime was prepared as a brown precipitate by adding an ammoniacal solution of copper sulphate (1 mol.) to a solution of oxalenediamidoxime (2 mol.) in water. The brown noncrystalline precipitate was washed well with hot water and then dried over sulphuric acid to constant weight. [Found : N, 37.2; Cu, 21.22. $\text{Cu}(\text{OxH})_2$ requires N, 37.66; Cu, 21.36 per cent].

Cupric oxalenediamidoxime chloride was obtained by Dubsy and Okac's method (*loc. cit.*) as a deep green crystalline powder when oxalenediamidoxime (1 mol.) was added to excess of copper chloride (3 mol.) and the solution allowed to evaporate slowly. [Found : N, 22.24; Cl, 27.9; Cu, 25.19. $\text{Cu}(\text{OxH}_2)_2\text{Cl}_2$ requires N, 22.19; Cl, 28.08; Cu, 25.16 per cent].

Cupric bis-oxalenediamidoxime chloride was obtained in deep green, shining crystals by adding a solution of oxalenediamidoxime (2 mol.) to a solution of cupric chloride (1 mol.). The aqueous solution of the compound gives brown coloured precipitate of the inner complex on treatment

with ammonia, the reaction being reversible as in the case of nickel. [Found: N, 30.0; Cl, 18.95; Cu, 17.05. $\text{Cu}(\text{OxH}_2)_2\text{Cl}_2$ requires N, 30.25; Cl, 19.14; Cu, 17.16 per cent].

Cupric bis-oxalenediamidoxime sulphate was obtained in deep green shining scales by partial evaporation of a solution containing copper sulphate (1 mol.) and oxalenediamidoxime (2 mol.). [Found: N, 27.95; Cu, 16.15; SO_4 , 22.92. $\text{Cu}(\text{OxH}_2)_2\text{SO}_4$ requires N, 28.33; Cu, 16.10; SO_4 , 24.28 per cent]. The substance is paramagnetic, ($\chi_e = 2.67 \times 10^{-6}$; $\mu = 1.65$ Bohr's magneton).

Mercuric oxalenediamidoxime monochloride was precipitated in small quantity on mixing aqueous solutions of mercuric chloride (5 g.) and oxalenediamidoxime (4.5 g.) in cold. The yellow precipitate was washed well and dried in air. (Found: Cl, 10.13; Hg, 56.4. ClHgOxH requires Cl, 10.06; Hg, 56.8 per cent).

Cobaltous bis-oxalenediamidoxime chloride hexahydrate was prepared after Schnackig by treating an aqueous solution of cobaltous chloride (1 mol.) with a solution of the dioxime (2 mol.). On slow evaporation, chocolate brown crystals were obtained which lose 6 molecules of water of crystallisation on drying at 110° [Found: N, 23.30; Cl, 14.52; Co, 12.83. $\text{Co}(\text{OxH}_2)_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 23.62; Cl, 14.96; Co, 12.44 per cent].

Cobaltous bis-oxalenediamidoxime chloride was obtained as a chocolate brown crystalline powder on treating a warm solution of anhydrous cobaltous chloride (1 mol.) in acetone with an acetone solution of oxalenediamidoxime (2 mol.). The crystals separated almost immediately on mixing the solutions and were found to have identical properties with the dehydrated compound of the previous salt. [Found: N, 30.20; Cl, 19.1; Co, 16.00. $\text{Co}(\text{OxH}_2)_2\text{Cl}_2$ requires N, 30.63; Cl, 19.4; Co, 16.12 per cent].

Diaminodioxalenediamidoxime Cobaltic Chloride.—To an ice-cold solution of cobaltous chloride (1 mol.), well cooled oxalene diamidoxime (2 mol.) solution was added, followed by enough ammonia to make the solution smell of the gas. A rapid current of air was passed through the mixture for about half an hour, filtered and allowed to crystallise in *vacuo*. Brown transparent crystals, soluble in water, readily decomposed by mineral acids. [Found: N, 38.2; Cl, 9.6; Co, 16.54. $(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Co}(\text{OxH})_2\text{Cl}$ requires N, 38.64; Cl, 9.8; Co, 16.26 per cent].

Dipyridinodi-oxalenediamidoxime Cobaltic Chloride.—Air was passed through an ice-cold solution containing cobaltous chloride (1 mol.), oxalenediamidoxime (2 mol.) and pyridine (2 mol.) for about half an hour. The solution was then filtered and allowed to evaporate slowly in *vacuo*. The product was recrystallised from alcohol. Deep brown, stout needles,

decomposed by dilute acids. [Found : N, 28.83 ; Cl, 7.1 ; Co, 12.26. $(C_5H_5N)_2Co(OxH)_2Cl$ requires N, 28.78 ; Cl, 7.3 ; Co, 12.12 per cent]. The magnetic susceptibility of the compound was practically nil.

Di-monoethylaminodi-oxalenediamidoxime cobaltic chloride was obtained as brown crystals by passing air for about half an hour through a well cooled solution of cobaltous chloride (1 mol.), dioxime (2 mol.) and a slight excess of 35% ethylamine. [Found : N, 33.23 ; Cl, 8.31 ; Co, 14.52. $(C_2H_5NH_2)_2Co(OxH)_2Cl$ requires N, 33.48 ; Cl, 8.47 ; Co, 14.41 per cent].

Di-isoquinolinodi-oxalenediamidoxime cobaltic chloride was precipitated as a brown powder by passing air through a well cooled aqueous alcoholic solution of cobaltous chloride (1 mol.), dioxime (2 mol.) and isoquinoline (2 mol.). The compound is similar to the pyridino complex and is decomposed by dilute acids. [Found : N, 23.95 ; Cl, 5.9 ; Co, 10.2. $(C_8H_7N)_2Co(OxH)_2Cl$ requires N, 23.88 ; Cl, 6.05 ; Co, 10.05 per cent].

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